

**TEACHING ENTREPRENEURSHIP EDUCATION THROUGH ACTIVITY-BASED
APPROACH IN FEDERAL COLLEGE OF EDUCATION (TECHNICAL) BICHI, KANO
STATE**

BY

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Abstract

Teaching Entrepreneurship Education has become an issue within the academic on how effective can be taught in order to meet the desire objectives. The inclusion of the course is helping students with skill and mindset in creating, developing and sustaining business. Entrepreneurship is towards making one to be creative or innovative in exploring entrepreneurial opportunity. Thus, the aim of the study is explore ways that will enhance the teaching of entrepreneurship education in our tertiary institutions. The study adopted survey and correlation design to determine appropriate method for teaching Entrepreneurship education in Federal College of Education (Technical) Bichi, Kano State. The study assessed the students' attitude/mind-set and appropriate methodology for teaching entrepreneurial education. The population comprises of 86 lecturers purposively selected and 50 students with ten (10) each randomly selected from five (5) schools. The instrument for data collection was a questionnaires design to elicit information on attitude and methodologies from students and lecturers respectively with pre-test and post-test administered for both control and experimental groups with conventional and activity-based teaching methods. The instrument was validated by two research experts. The reliability coefficient of 0.75 was obtained through a Cronbach Alpha analysis of the copies of the instrument used for pilot testing. Frequency count, simple percentage and t-test were the statistical tools used for data analysis. Findings revealed among others that some students are positive on their perspective on the need for entrepreneurship education, teaching methods such as simulation, case study, computer assisted instruction and activity-based methods among others identified as suitable for teaching entrepreneurial education. Based on the findings, it is recommended among others that priority should be given to the use of activity-based method while teaching Entrepreneurship education at all level in Colleges of Education.

Keywords: Teaching, Entrepreneurial Education, Conventional Methods, Activity-Based Method, Assessment, Evaluation

1.0 Introduction

Wealth and majority of jobs are created by small businesses started by entrepreneurially minded individuals, many of whom go on to create big businesses. People exposed to entrepreneurship frequently express that they have more opportunity to exercise creative freedoms, higher self-esteem, and an overall greater sense of control over their own lives (National Content Standards, 2016). The inclusion of entrepreneurship education in our educational curriculum emanated from the situation of unemployability our students found themselves after graduation. Most a time a graduate look on government for job that is not forthcoming. In a blog discussion by Shane (2010) Harry argued that “depending on the quality, quantity and context within which it is experienced, I can assure all of you that entrepreneurship education and training can, and often does have some very positive outcomes” on business initiation, development and sustainability. On the same ground Greene (2013) observed that whoever wants to venture into business can freely do it anytime, anywhere...however, entrepreneurship education could help an entrepreneur in many ways, and it could give more schematic and clearer theories and more knowledge about the business. Therefore, education and entrepreneurial abilities are both essential for a good and futuristic entrepreneur.

1.1 Research Questions

The study was guided by the following questions:

1. What are the attitudes (mind-set) of students towards Entrepreneurship Education in Federal College of Education (Technical) Bichi, Kano State?
2. What are the methodologies and strategies that could be adopted for effective teaching of entrepreneurship education in College of Education?
3. What are the Activity Based Approach for implementing these methodologies and strategies in Colleges of Education?

1.2 Objectives of the Study

The objective of the study was to identify suitable approaches or methods for teaching entrepreneurship in Colleges of Education with reference to Federal College of Education (Technical) Bichi. Specifically, the study focused on:

- a. The attitude (mind-set) of students towards Entrepreneurship Education in Federal College of Education (Technical) Bichi, Kano State

- b. Identify effective methodologies and strategies for teaching entrepreneurship education in Colleges of Education
- c. Device means of implementing these methodologies for teaching entrepreneurship in Colleges of Education.

1.3 Research Hypothesis

There is no significant difference in the responses of Control and Experimental group of students taught curriculum content of GSE 224 (Entrepreneurship in Education) Using Conventional and Activity Based Approach.

1.4 Concepts Clarification

Key Concepts in this research is hereby presented as used in this work

- a. *Entrepreneurship*: The process of designing, launching, and running a business or enterprise, often with the goal of earning a profit.
- b. *Activity-Based Approach*: A teaching methodology that focuses on hands-on, experiential learning activities that encourage students to explore, create, and innovate.
- c. *Teaching Entrepreneurship*: The process of educating students about the principles, practices, and skills required to become successful entrepreneurs.

1.5 Research Variables

The followings are the research variables guiding the conduct of the research.

- a. Independent Variable: The activity-based approach to teaching entrepreneurship.
- b. Dependent Variable: The students' entrepreneurial knowledge, skills, and attitudes.
- c. Moderating Variables: Factors that may influence the effectiveness of the activity-based approach, such as student motivation, prior experience, and access to resources.

1.6 Theoretical Framework

The activity-based approach to teaching entrepreneurship is rooted in several theoretical frameworks, which include:

- a. Experiential Learning Theory (ELT): ELT posits that learning occurs through direct experience and reflection (Kolb, 1984).
- b. Social Cognitive Theory (SCT): SCT suggests that learning occurs through observation, imitation, and reinforcement (Bandura, 1977).
- c. Entrepreneurial Learning Theory (ELT): ELT emphasizes the importance of experiential learning, experimentation, and iteration in entrepreneurial development (Cope, 2005).

1.7 Problem Statement/Justification

Teaching entrepreneurship is presently carried out in the conventional way, in a classroom where the teacher enters class and deliver lecture theoretically and gives written notes or prepared handout to the students. This teaching methodology is not readily yielding the desired result in terms of understanding the content and even applying the knowledge in another life. Thus, restricting entrepreneurship to classroom lesson alone is not enough and “if we do not come up with a rigorous way to teach entrepreneurship there is going to be a backlash” (Tomkins-Berg & Miller, 2015). The current system lacks the practical activity needed to motivate the students and move them to develop the interest in business creation. The method is deficient in experience sharing from an entrepreneur or going to field trip/excursion that will exposes the students to more business setting. Similarly, the conventional method lacks the provision for business modeling or life business feasibility report and the effective means of assessments on the side of the lecturers. Institutions of higher learning establish entrepreneurship centers with the purpose of offering training in selected trades to the students but not teaching them entrepreneurial skill development and the training is not connected to the area of study of the students, meaning labouring the students with another learning task. By doing so, the students will only attend the class if it happens to be compulsory for them to pass the prescribe exams but not acquiring the expected skill and experience. Therefore, the study assessed the relevance of teaching entrepreneurship education using Activity-based method and compares its performance with those taught with conventional method. The study further analyzed the significance of different component of entrepreneurship education programme used in imparting entrepreneurial skills, qualities and mindset of students in Federal College of Education (Technical) Bichi. Kano State, Nigeria.

2.0 Literature Review

Entrepreneurship education is receiving due considerations with the fact that there is need to redirect the young ones towards self-employment against the belief that government is to provide jobs at the point of graduation. Zhang et al. in Hussaini (2015) concluded that despite the importance of entrepreneurship education, it is unusual to observe that few studies have been conducted to see the impact of entrepreneurship education on intention for business creativity. However, Shane (2010) observed that “studies by researchers at the University of Arizona, US and other institutions have found that people who have received entrepreneurship education perform better at running their own businesses.” On this note research demonstrated empirically the impact of different component taught during entrepreneurial education course on the entrepreneurial education and intentions (Hussaini, 2015).

On the traditional or conventional method of teaching, Korakakis (2014) believes that “though still very important, schools seem to be putting almost all of their focus on traditional methods, what is missing in many elementary and secondary curriculums are techniques that will teach students to solve future problems, collaborate with others, take calculated risk and learn from failure. This tradition is associated to the misconception between teaching entrepreneurship is synonymous to teaching about sales (Korakakis, 2014). However, participating in entrepreneurship activities, students can gain skills such as, autonomy, leadership, creativity, initiative, perseverance, self-confidence, sense of responsibility and solidarity (National Content Standards, 2016). Most importantly, all of these are transferable skills that will give them necessary tools to excel whether they aim to be entrepreneurs or intrapreneurs. Considering the importance of entrepreneurship education today, what entrepreneurship activity-based learning will do is to instill confidence in the students during their school life. To provide them with knowledge and skill in enterprise and make them realize the potentialities in them for self-actualization. By this they are thus able to see that they can accomplish whatever they set up to do. When a young person realizes that he holds the key to his/her future, this equals to limitless possibilities. Hence, the goal here is to teach students to become entrepreneurs or ways to grow the economy (Korakakis, 2014). Earlier to this, the Coleman Foundation in 1981 profound a programme called ‘Entrepreneurship Education Impact Plan’ comprising of curricular and co-curricular components in the school curriculum. This is a strategy within the curriculum aimed to foster development of core skills and the promotion of entrepreneurship as interdisciplinary learning. The plan also seeks to improve the quality and quantity of experiential activities across disciplines that develop applied knowledge and

experiences in self-employment. Glangchai (2013) opines that “entrepreneurial education is more than just building a business plan and marketing a product. It is about learning how to recognize opportunities and capitalize on them and that is a skill every young professional should have”. These educational exercises give students a greater sense of self-control and higher self-esteem. When programmes utilize hands-on and experiential learning techniques there are chances of developing innovative thinking skills.

2.1 Teaching Entrepreneurship for Entrepreneurial Skill

In the traditional or conventional classroom setting teaching/instruction is dominated by the teacher, whereby the students are left with less or no much to do than what came from the teacher. At the end the students lack the initiative and innovative skills of creativity required of them. Moreover, teaching entrepreneurship in the traditional mode alone contributes less in acquiring the needed qualities or skills of entrepreneur which include self-confidence, autonomy, a strong work ethic, ambition, empathy, and “an internal locus of control” as essential in giving the students the drive and personal abilities to make their goals a reality (Glangchai, 2013). Similarly, sharing experience plays major role in the success of business. This point is shared with Garland in Shane (2010) that “hearing from entrepreneurs that have walked the walked, their successes and their failures” will add to the chances of students to be become successful entrepreneurs. Some notable entrepreneurship education programs and pedagogies include:

- a. Babson College's Entrepreneurship Program: Known for its experiential learning approach and emphasis on entrepreneurial mindset. (Morris, Kuratko, & Cornwall, 2013, Katz & Green, 2009).
- b. Stanford University's Entrepreneurship Network: Offers a range of programs and resources, including mentorship, funding, and networking opportunities. (Leslie, 2013, Hart, 2011)
- c. Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT)'s Entrepreneurship Program: Focuses on developing students' entrepreneurial skills through hands-on experiences and real-world projects. (Litan & Mitchell, 2011)

Achieving this level, Polzin (2015) opines that “creating an entrepreneurial culture in schools or colleges and in some cases support local start-ups and small businesses clear ways for entrepreneurial development. To meet the designing objectives, Rullani (2016) posits that “designing courses in entrepreneurship education by bringing theory and practice together to co-evolve is one good way of teaching entrepreneurship”. Practice-based and theory-based learning <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16216697>

package should be jointly taught iteratively thereby engage the students in learning-by-doing activities by introducing novel projects, and allowing them to discover not only what tools, skills and contacts they need, but also what kind of attitude, mind-set and perspective they will need to help them more successfully into their careers or ventures. All these require close cooperation between the different stakeholders and the willingness to enter innovative learning instead of sticking to traditional learning pathways” (Polzin, 2015).

2.2 Definition of Entrepreneurship

Many scholars forwarded definitions of entrepreneurship from a specific point of view while others on general note. Among those on perception of entrepreneurship include Shrivastava & Shrivastava (2013) that entrepreneurship refers to (a) Owning and managing a business, i.e. occupational entrepreneurship, and (b) Entrepreneurial behavior in the sense of seizing an opportunity. Others like Shane & Venkataraman in Afolabi (2015) defined entrepreneurship as “an activity that involves the discovery, evaluation and exploitation of opportunities to introduce new goods and services, ways of organizing, marketing and processing of raw material through organize efforts that previously had not existed”. Therefore, entrepreneurial education should prepare students to lead rather than to follow and operate within a global parameter than within a parochial perspective. In a nutshell, entrepreneurship education should give training and impart necessary skills to the individual who shall be self-reliant economically.

2.3 Teaching Entrepreneurship Education

Traditionally, teaching takes place in the classroom. However, in any learning situation and for effective delivery, meeting the course content and achieving the objectives are determined by the methodology used. Hence, with nature of entrepreneurship, the mode of teaching according to Blenker, Dreisler & Kjelden (2006) “studies indicate that educating and teaching for and not just about entrepreneurship should include different theories and methodology from the ones ordinarily applied”. With high interest posed on entrepreneurship education, our institutions of higher learning are tasked with paradigm shift in teaching methodology from the conventional or classroom-centered teaching to activity-based method in order to meet the objectives of teaching entrepreneurship for business initiation, development and sustainability.

In the 9-year Basic Education Curriculum, Senior Secondary Education Curriculum and 34 Trade/Entrepreneur Curriculum developed by NERDC for use at the senior secondary education level in the country, every student, irrespective of his or her field of study is expected to study 5 core subjects and one trade entrepreneurship subject. This foundation knowledge is expected to be <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16216697>

built on through entrepreneurial education courses in tertiary institutions with a view of developing students' interest/mind-set towards embracing entrepreneurship in the later part of their life for sustainable livelihood.

By this trend our institutions across are in need to put more effort in entrepreneurship and innovation through research to meet “this unaccustomed extramural role that frequently requires new ways of thinking and new ways of doing things” (Blenker et al, 2006). Many experienced business people, economists, and educators believe that fostering a robust entrepreneurial culture will maximize individual and collective economic and social success on a local, national, and global scale (National Content Standards, 2016). Presently, attention is focusing on effective ways of delivering entrepreneurial education, which can make it applicable to all areas of study. The growing number of students shunning traditional employment opportunities to become entrepreneurs has caught some business schools, faculty and administrators off-guard (Charney & Libecap, 2012). There is a need for the students to develop strong professional, enterprising and innovative competences in their field of specialization. Therefore, teaching entrepreneurship provides the students with the incentive and mindset to either start their own business (entrepreneurship) or to detect new commercial opportunities in an existing organization or business (intrapreneurship) for self-reliance and sustainable livelihood.

2.4 New Approaches to the Teaching of Entrepreneurship

Considering the nature of entrepreneurship and putting in mind the methodology for effective delivery, there is need for paradigm shift to new approach in teaching the concept effectively. Often times educational institutions are criticized for not giving students the necessary tools to cope in the real world”. What entrepreneurship activity-based learning does from the get-go is that it teaches students how to recognize opportunities and how to act on them. Awasthi (1991) proposed ways for promoting entrepreneurship training through:

- a. Entrepreneurship orientation and awareness programme: For inculcating the spirit of entrepreneurship at start-up stage.
- b. Reflective practice gives permission to students to take time, think, and absorb the learning of their practice-based curriculum.
- c. New enterprise creation which involves comprehensive training package to develop competences in trainees, leading to self-employment.

- d. Setting up an enterprise thus creating further employment. The method aimed at developing knowledge, skill and attitudes in a potential entrepreneur to make him/her an actual manager.

This is not a “skill easily forgotten according to Korakakis (2014) when properly implemented into different facets of an educational curriculum”. Both Korakakis (2014) and Greene (2013) believed that the above teaching techniques are explicit and gave room to involve practical activity for which students undertook.

An action plan designed by Norway for the period 2009 to 2014 aimed at strengthening a culture for entrepreneurship and collaboration between education, training and working for life, which was launched in 2004, revised in 2006 and evaluated in 2008 showed marked increase of number of students that participated in different types of entrepreneurship training. The conclusion made was that “it is necessary to expand efforts in a number of areas so as to promote entrepreneurship in teaching and learning at all levels” (Norway, 2010). With this, schools should also consider the benefits of teaching traditional subjects with an entrepreneurial approach by implementing entrepreneurship activity-based learning approach into an existing school curriculum (Korakakis, 2014). Taking this upon will add value to the educational system and as a means of making an individual a contributor to the development of the society.

3.0 Research Methodology

The study adopted Survey and Correlational Experimental Design. Survey research design in the opinion of Ali (2006) is a descriptive study which uses sample of an investigation to document, describe and explain what is in existence or non-existence on the presence status of phenomenon been investigated. In survey study, views and facts are collected through questionnaire, interviews among others, analyzed and use for answering research questions. While the correlational design assisted in identifying the relationships that exist between variables (Control and Experimental group) without manipulation after being taught entrepreneurship course content using conventional teaching method for the control group and Activity-based method for the treatment group in order to determine their effectiveness for teaching entrepreneurial education in Colleges of Education

3.1 Area of the Study

The study was carried out in Federal College of Education (Technical) Bichi located along old Bagwai road and directly opposite Government Secondary School Bichi. The College has seven

schools but five were selected because of their peculiarities in relation to entrepreneurial education to be involved in the study. These schools are Business Education, Science Education, Technical Education, Vocational Education and Primary Education.

3.2 Population and Sample of the Study

The population for the study comprises of Eighty-six (86) lecturers purposively selected and fifty (50) students from the entire population of NCE 111 students randomly sampled for the study out of three hundred and seventy (370). The fifty (50) selected students for the study were divided into two groups; Control group and Treatment group of twenty-five (25) each. The table below shows the number of selected students per school and according to trade.

S/NO	Schools	Number of Students
01	School of Secondary. Education (Technical)	10
02	School of Secondary Education (Vocational)	10
03	School of Secondary Education (Business)	10
04	School of Secondary Education (Science)	10
05	School of Early Childhood Care and Primary Education	10
Total		50

3.3 Instrument for Data Collection

The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire titled: Teaching Entrepreneurship Education Through Activity-Based Approach in Federal College of Education (Tech.) Bichi, Kano State. The 32 items questionnaire was made up of section A which is meant to elicit information on personal data of the respondents and section B was used to obtained data on the attitude/mind-set of students towards entrepreneurship education, methodologies and strategies for effective teaching of entrepreneurial education and identification of suitable activities based approach for implementing the teaching of entrepreneurial education in Federal College of Education (Technical) Bichi. The section B part of the questionnaire has Yes/No response and four-point response options of Strongly Agreed (SA), Agreed (A), Disagreed (D) and Strongly Disagreed (SD) with corresponding value of 4, 3, 2, and 1 respectively.

3.4 Experimental Procedures: The procedure adopted involved subjecting the two group of students (Conventional and Treatment Group) to pre-test in order to ascertain their current level of awareness on entrepreneurship education and taught using conventional method before administering treatment to the two group (Conventional and Activity Based Approach). A post-test was also administered on the two groups for the purpose of comparing both the pre-test and

post-test results for determining the appropriate methods for teaching entrepreneurship education in College of Education. They include:

- 2.1.A Control group involved five (5) NCE III students from each of the five (5) schools, making a total of twenty-five (25). The group was assessed based on the conventional or traditional teaching method.
- 2.1.B Treatment group also involved five (5) NCE III students each from the five (5) schools, making total of twenty-five (25) students. The twenty-five (25) students were further divided into three groups and posted to different environment where they were exposed to activity-based teaching to ease the task of data collection from the field as listed below:
 - 2.1.B.1 Excursion and Exhibition
 - 2.1.B.2 Lectures from invited guest lecturers
 - 2.1.B.3 Practical exercise involving series of entrepreneurial activities based on their area of specialization and from the course content.
 - 2.1.B.4 Use of slide and transparencies on business ideas and entrepreneurship.
 - 2.1.B.5 Planning business and preparing feasibility reports to be developed into finished products.

3.5 Method of Data Collection: The data for the study were collected with the help of two (2) research assistants hired for administration and retrieval of the instrument. Copies of the questionnaires were retrieved from the research assistants at an agreed time and location for data analysis.

3.6 Method of Data Analysis: The data generated by the study were analyzed using descriptive statistics such as frequency count, simple percentage for the research questions while t-test was used to analyzed the hypothesis of no significant difference at relevant degree of freedom. In taking decision on the research questions, any item whose percentage score is above 50% is considered accepted. On the hypotheses tested, the hypotheses of no significant difference were accepted where the P-value is greater than 0.05 levels and this indicated that there was no significant difference in the responses of the two groups of respondents. If the p-value is less than 0.05 levels, this indicated that the hypothesis of no significant difference on the responses of the two groups of respondents was rejected.

4.0 Research Result Analysis

The analyses of the results were presented in the tables below:

Research Question 1: What are the attitudes (mind-set) of students towards Entrepreneurship Education in Federal College of Education (Technical) Bichi, Kano State?

Responses of Students' attitude (mind-set) towards Entrepreneurship Education in Federal College of Education (Technical) Bichi, Kano State (Students = 50)

S/No	Students Attitude (mind-set) towards Entrepreneurship Education ITEMS	Response Options		
		YES	NO	TOTAL
01	Entrepreneurship education is an interesting subject	46, 92%	04, 8%	100%
02	Entrepreneurship education lessons increased my interest in a career in entrepreneurship	36, 72%	14, 28%	100%
03	I enjoy learning new things in entrepreneurial education	42, 84%	08, 16%	100%
04	Entrepreneurial skills and its application in real life often occur to me on regular basis because of my interest	32, 64%	18, 36%	100%
05	Whenever I observe people complaining about some products/services, I think of the market	29, 58%	21, 42%	100%
06	I frequently imagine the possibility of success that certain products/services could have in a certain market.	30, 60%	20, 40%	100%
07	I believe I am very capable of translating entrepreneurship ideas, organizing and executing plan to be successful.	39, 78%	11, 22%	100%
08	I have all the capacity needed to realize my entrepreneurship professional/academic future	22, 44%	28, 56%	100%
09	I would love to practice all I have learnt in entrepreneurship education when I leave school	48, 96%	02, 4%	100%
10	I can easily relate with other persons, even with those I still do not know	42, 84%	08, 16%	100%
11	I love planning a head to attain success in Entrepreneurial activities.	44, 88%	06, 12%	100%

The data in table 1 above revealed that all the items except 8 had their percentages above 50% indicating that the responses outlined the attitude of students towards entrepreneurship education in Federal College of Education (Technical) Bichi.

Research Question 2: What are the methodologies and effective strategies for teaching entrepreneurship Education in Federal College of Education (Technical) Bichi, Kano State?

Responses of Lecturers on the Methodologies and Effective Strategies for Teaching Entrepreneurship Education in Federal College of Education (Technical) Bichi, Kano State (Lecturers= 86)

S/No	Methodologies in Teaching Entrepreneurship Education ITEMS	Response Options				
		SA	A	D	SD	T0tal
01	Simulation instruction Method	30, 35%	13, 15%	31, 36%	12, 14%	86, 100%
02	Case study instruction Method	46, 54%	23, 28%	10, 12%	07, .08%	86, 100%
03	Business plan creation instruction Method	37, 43%	46, 54%	03, 03%	00, 0%	86, 100%
04	Problem-solving instruction Method	30, 35%	32, 37%	21, 24%	03, .03%	86, 100%
05	Team Teaching instruction Method	57, 66%	29, 34%	00, 0%	00, 0%	86, 100%
06	computer-assisted instruction Strategy	40, 47%	46, 53%	00, 0%	00, 0%	86, 100%
07	Conventional Method	23, 28%	15, 17%	33, 38%	15, 17%	86, 100%

The data in table 2 above indicated that all the items had their (Strongly Agreed and Agreed) percentages above 50% except item 1 and item 7 where both side had 50% each. This revealed that all the teaching methods identified can be used for teaching entrepreneurship education effectively except conventional method which is the most popular method currently in used in Federal College of Education (Technical) Bichi.

Research question 3: What are the effective strategies for teaching entrepreneurship education in Federal Colleges of Education (Technical) Bichi?

S/No	Effective Strategies for Teaching Entrepreneurship Education ITEMS	Response Options				
		SA	A	D	SD	TOTAL
01	Co-designs the Entrepreneurial curriculum and subjects with entrepreneurs and alumni	24, 8%	46, 53%	14, 16%	02, .023%	86, 100%

02	Teachers exploring research output in the execution of entrepreneurial activities with students	22, 26%	42, 49%	17, 20%	05, 06%	86, 100%
03	Create good conditions and rapour to foster co-operation between employees and departments	34, 40%	38, 44%	14, 16%	00, 0%	86, 100%
04	Engage and recruit individuals with private sector experience (lectures, seminars, practical experience sharing) for teaching entrepreneurial skills in schools	56, 65%	30, 34%	00, 0%	00, 0%	86, 100%
05	Recognizes best entrepreneurship practitioners (e.g. entrepreneurs / mentors) and practices (e.g. collaborative projects with businesses) outside the school for partnership	61, 71%	25, 29%	00, 0%	00, 0%	86, 100%
06	Regular assessment of goals related to entrepreneurship and innovation achievement are important at the level of university and faculty/department	43, 50%	41, 48%	02, .023 %	00, 0%	86, 100%
07	provides diverse informal learning opportunities to stimulate the development of entrepreneurial skills (free training courses, entrepreneurship days.	34, 40%	32, 37%	18, 21%	06, .07%	86, 100%
08	Provide supports for staff to move from idea generation to business creation through training, mentoring, counselling on entrepreneurship among students	49, 57%	32, 37%	04, .05 %	01, .01%	86, 100%
09	Provide a structural unit that have strong links with incubators, science parks and other external initiatives supporting entrepreneurship	43, 50%	32, 37%	11, .13 %	00, 0%	86, 100%
10	staff should carry out research and development on entrepreneurship in cooperation with students and external partners for sharing ideas	44, 51%	36, 42%	06, .07 %	00, 0%	86, 100%
11	Make provision to facilitates technology and knowledge transfer through contact with businesses and other relevant organizations	46, 54%	40, 47%	00, 0%	00, 0%	86, 100%
12	Promote Self-instruction on entrepreneurship activities	32, 37%	38, 44%	16, 19%	00, 0%	86, 100%
13	Organizing competitions for students in entrepreneurship	42, 49%	42, 49%	02, .023 %	00, 0%	86, 100%
14	Excursions to business organizations for on the spot interactions with entrepreneurs	52, 60%	29, 38%	05, .06 %	00, 0%	86, 100%

The data in table 3 above revealed that all the items had their (Strongly Agreed and Agreed) percentages above 50%. This indicated that all the strategies identified by this study can be utilized

with any of the above methods in table 2.1 for effective teaching of entrepreneurial education in Federal Colleges of Education (Technical) Bichi.

Research Question 4: What is the Activity-Based Approach that could be used for teaching entrepreneurial education in Federal College of Education (Technical) Bichi, Kano State?

Response of Treatment Group on the use of Activity-Based Approach for teaching of Entrepreneurial Education in Federal College of Education (Technical) Bichi, Kano State (Treatment Group=25 Students)

S/NO	ITEMS	Response in Group Using Percentage						
		Group A (8, students)		Group B (8, students)		Group C (9, students)		Total
		Scores above average	Scores below average	Scores above average	Scores below average	Scores above average	Scores below average	Total
01	Embarking on Excursion and Exhibition to relevant entrepreneurial set up for study and documentation	6 (75%)	2 (25%)	7 (88%)	1 (12%)	6 (67%)	3 (33%)	25 (100%)
02	Lectures from invited guest lecturers on Entrepreneurship	4 (50%)	4 (50%)	5 (63%)	3 (37%)	5 (56%)	4 (44%)	25 (100%)
03	Practical exercise involving series of entrepreneurial activities based on their area of specialization and course content.	6 (75%)	2 (25%)	6 (75%)	2 (25%)	7 (78%)	2 (22%)	25 (100%)
04	Use of slide and transparencies on business ideas and entrepreneurship	7 (88%)	1 (12%)	6 (75%)	2 (25%)	6 (67%)	3 (33%)	25 (100%)
05	Preparing business plan and feasibility reports to be developed into finished products.	4 (50%)	4 (50%)	5 (63%)	3 (37%)	5 (56%)	4 (44%)	25 (100%)

The data in table 4 above on item 1 revealed that 19 students representing 76% out of 25 students had performance scores above average indicating that the use of excursion and exhibition enhances students' skills acquisition in entrepreneurial education, while the remaining 6 students representing 24% performed below average. Also, the data on item 2 in the table shows that 14 students out of 25 representing 56% also had their performance scores above average on listening to lecture on entrepreneurship from invited guest while the performance of the remaining 11 students representing 44% was below average. Also, item 3 revealed that 19 students representing 76% out of 25 had performance scores above average on the use of practical exercise involving series of entrepreneurial activities based on their area of specialization and course content while the remaining 6 students representing 24% performed below average. Furthermore, the data on item 4 shows that 19 students representing 76% out of 25 had performance scores above average indicating that the use of slide and transparencies on business ideas and entrepreneurship enhance student performance in entrepreneurship education while the remaining 6 students representing 24% perform below average and finally, data on item 5 in table 4 revealed that 14 students out of 25 representing 56% also had their performance scores above average on the preparation of business plan and feasibility reports to be developed into finished products, while the remaining 11 students representing 44% performed below average. The results show that the use of activity-based method is effective for teaching entrepreneurial education in Colleges of Education as majority of the students subjected to treatment in different group performed above average.

Hypothesis

Variables	N	\bar{x}	SD	df	t	p – value
Control Group	25	25.2800	10.94121	48	0.395	0.000
Experimental Group	25	48.9200	11.58634			

The results of the hypothesis tested showed that the alpha value at 0.05 > than the p-value at 0.000. Indicating a significant difference between students taught curriculum content of GSE 224 (Entrepreneurship in Education) using conventional and activity-based approach. Therefore, the null hypothesis on significant difference in them earn scores of control and experimental group of students taught curriculum content of GSE 224 (Entrepreneurship in Education) using conventional and activity-based approach is rejected.

4.0 Discussion of Findings

The results of the study revealed several attitude or mind set of students towards the teaching of entrepreneurial education. Such attitude includes declaring entrepreneurship education is an interesting subject, lessons increasing students' interest in a career in entrepreneurship education, enjoying learning new things in entrepreneurial education, entrepreneurial skills and its application in real life often occur to students on regular basis because of their interest among others. The finding of this study is in agreement with the findings of Ahmed and Sulyman, (2022), on the Assessment of Students' Attitudes towards Entrepreneurship Development Initiatives in Kwara State University, Malete (Case Study of Faculty of Communication and Information Science) "where it was revealed that majority of the respondents, 86% are interested in the entrepreneurship initiatives in their school and that the level of interest of the students can influence their attitude towards the entrepreneurship initiatives and motivate them to go extra miles on making the initiatives work for their advantage, thereby helping the students in becoming self-dependent and establish their businesses after graduation,

On methodologies and effective strategies for teaching of entrepreneurial education, the study identified simulation, case study, team teaching, computer-assisted instructions among others. These findings are in line with the findings of Gift, Joy and Gift-Eke (2023) on the Adequacy of Teaching Techniques for Improved Entrepreneurship Education in Universities in Rivers State where it was revealed that majority of the business educators were familiar with the four teaching techniques that were assessed in the study and adopt them when delivering lectures. The result also indicated that the adequacy of expository technique, games and simulations techniques, design-based technique and reflective practice technique in the transference of entrepreneurship skills to students in the institution. Also, the findings of Okoye (2017) on Strategies Considered Effective by Business Educators for Teaching Entrepreneurship Education in Tertiary Institutions in Anambra State which revealed that business plan, simulation and computer-assisted instruction are effective strategies for teaching entrepreneurship education in tertiary institutions agreed with the findings of this study on strategies for effective teaching of entrepreneurial education in Federal College of Education (Technical) Bichi.

On activity-based teaching approach, the study identified embarking on excursion and exhibition, lectures from invited guest lecturers on entrepreneurship, use of slide and transparencies on

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business ideas and entrepreneurship, preparing business plan and feasibility reports among others activities to enhance skill and mindset development. These are in line with the findings of Abdulhameed, Amina., Kehinde & Afolake, (2021) on Entrepreneurship Education Instruction Strategies and Graduates' Self-Reliance which indicated that "simulation, case study, business plan creation, problem-solving and team working instruction strategies were among the most suitable instructional strategies for teaching entrepreneurship education".

The results of the hypothesis tested showed that majority of the students' scores increased in experimental group as compared to the control group. The mean value indicated that participants from experimental group showed more achievement in post-test with higher mean score of 48.9200 while the control group students scored 25.2800. The post-lesson survey showed that majority of the students found the activity-based teaching to be more interesting than lecture/ conventional teaching method.

5.0 Conclusion and Recommendations

Based on the results and discussion, this study concluded that students' attitude in the College is positive towards entrepreneurship education and the use of activity-based teaching enhances students' motivation and improves their skills acquisition in entrepreneurship and academic achievement. The following recommendations are proposed on the basis of result of the study:

1. Entrepreneurship lecture at all level in Colleges of Education be conducted using activity-based approach to enhance and develop higher order thinking skills among the students.
2. Teacher training programme should include activity-based teaching to enhance teachers' teaching skills.
3. More activity-based approaches should developed to complement existence once to take care of all field of studies since entrepreneurship education cut across all courses.

6.0 Further Studies

The result indicates the effectiveness of activity-based approach even though lecture method cannot be totally neglected. Similarly, environmental factor plays significant role in the choice of strategy among the various activity-based approaches in teaching entrepreneurship education in tertiary institutions in Nigeria. The work is recommending further research on handling entrepreneurial education in high institutions of learning in Nigeria. It is the opinion of the

researchers that what perception shall we develop to effectively deliver the course content, is it by teaching or by training.

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